

In well-reclaimed soil neither 10-cm nor 20-cm spacings yielded higher. During 1976 highest yield was at 15-cm spacing and 5 seedlings/ hill. Although general yield levels increased with plant populations and with soil improvement,

the difference in yield between the 2 best treatments (4 and 5 seedlings/ hill) narrowed to become statistically equal. Maximum grain yields of 6.5 and 6.6 t/ha during 1977 and 1978 were at 15-cm spacing and 4 seedlings/hill. 🌾

Effect of spacing and plant population (2, 3,4, and 5 seedlings/hill) on rice yield in partially and well-reclaimed alkali soils of Kumarganj (Faizabad), India.

Spacing (cm)	Gypsum ^a (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)			
		2	3	4	5
<i>Pusa 2-21 (1976)</i>					
10	6	1.2	1.5	1.6	2.1
	12	1.2	1.6	1.8	2.2
15	6	1.0	1.3	1.7	2.1
	12	1.6	2.1	3.1	3.8
20	6	0.8	1.1	1.4	1.7
	12	1.5	1.9	2.2	2.7
LSD (0.05)		0.3			
<i>Java (1977)</i>					
10	6	4.3	4.7	5.1	5.5
	12	5.5	6.0	5.3	4.8
15	6	3.8	4.2	4.7	5.2
	12	5.1	5.5	6.5	6.3
20	6	3.5	3.9	4.3	4.6
	12	5.0	5.3	5.9	6.2
LSD (0.05)		0.5			
<i>Jaya (1978)</i>					
10	6	4.1	4.5	5.0	5.3
	12	5.3	5.6	5.4	4.8
15	6	3.6	4.0	4.5	4.9
	12	5.2	5.8	6.6	6.4
20	6	3.5	3.7	4.1	4.5
	12	4.9	5.3	5.7	6.1
LSD (0.05)		0.4			

^aGypsum was applied only once, in 1976.

Optimum spacing and nitrogen for medium-duration rice

Syed Nazeer Peeran and B. V. Anandan, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Tirur 602025, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, India

A 1982 experiment during samba (July-August to November-December) at PES, Tirur, showed that Ponni and IR20 yields increased at 20 × 20 cm rice plant spacing, regardless of the level of nitrogen applied (see table). 🌾

Effect of nitrogen levels and spacings on rice yield, Tirur, India, 1982 samba.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Ponni yield (t/ha)		IR20 yield (t/ha)	
	20 × 10 cm	20 × 20 cm	20 × 10 cm	20 × 20 cm
0	3.4	3.9	3.3	3.7
10	4.0	4.4	3.7	4.1
20	4.2	4.9	4.2	4.6
30	4.6	5.1	4.6	5.0
Mean	4.1	4.6	4.0	4.4
	CD		CD	
Nitrogen level	0.3**		0.2**	
Spacing	0.3**		0.2**	

Environment and its influence

Variations and associations in rice physiological growth parameters

S. K. Shrivastava and P. K. Saxena, Agricultural Botany Department, JNKVV, Jabalpur 482004, India

Grain productivity can be improved by using component breeding, which assumes productivity is associated with growth parameters and their heritability. Direct and indirect gene action related to productivity and growth traits should be known. This study hypothesizes level of improvement can be predicted by calculating the genetic coefficient of variation using heritability estimates.

Jaya, Kranti, JR 16-15-2, JR25-13-8, Madhuri, Garima, Ratna, Anupama, JR15-55-2, and IR36 were grown in a randomized block design with three replications at JNKVV Research Farm during July 1978-79. Growth parameters were evaluated every 2 weeks.

Physiological growth parameters among varieties varied significantly. Means of individual characteristics and the general mean also differed (Table 1). Coefficient of variation for genotype (gcv) ranged from 1.05 relative growth rate (RGR) to 25.99 leaf area ratio (LAR). Coefficient of variation for phenotype (pcv) ranged from 15.02 net assimilation rate (NAR) to 50.43 RGR. The gcv was equally higher in leaf area index (LAI) and crop growth rate (CGR), indicating the level of possible improvement.

Heritability values for all characteristics exhibited wide variations: range of 21.1 to 89.6. Heritability estimates were high for RGR followed by seed yield and leaf parameter (leaf weight ratio [LWR], LAR, and LAI). NAR and specific leaf area (SLA) had lower heritability values, reflecting environmental influence. Maximum genetic improvement was recorded for LAI and LAR

Positive, significant associations of LAI were recorded with leaf area dura-

Table 1. Estimates of variations in physiological parameters,^a Jabalpur, India, 1978-79.

	LAI	LAR	LWR	SLA	RGR	CGR	NAR	Seed yield (t/ha)
Mean	3.38	63.17	.268	229.1	.046	31.63	10.58	4.75
Minimum	1.81	16.91	.15	105.6	.016	13.67	7.63	3.08
Maximum	4.38	82.35	.35	330.9	.083	50.27	12.36	5.74
Phenotypic variance	1.03	359.52	.004	3766.4	.00054	107.06	2.54	7.99
Genotypic variance	0.77	269.65	.003	858.0	.00048	63.00	0.54	6.53
Environmental variance	0.26	89.87	.001	2908.4	.00056	44.06	3.08	1.46
pcv	30.05	30.02	24.88	26.79	50.43	32.69	15.02	18.81
gcv	25.96	25.99	21.66	23.54	1.05	25.09	6.92	16.99
h ² B (%)	74.6	75.0	75.7	22.7	89.6	58.0	21.1	81.6
G.A.	8.22	29.29	0.104	28.70	0.043	12.36	0.69	15.03
G.A. as % of mean	243.28	46.37	38.81	12.53	93.24	39.07	6.54	31.62

^a LAI = leaf area index, LAR = leaf area ratio, LWR = leaf weight ratio, SLA = specific leaf area, RGR = relative growth rate, CGR = crop growth rate, NAR = net assimilation rate, pcv = coefficient of variation for phenotype, gcv = coefficient of variation for genotype.

tion (LAD), LWR, seed yield, and SLA; of LAR with LAD, SLA, and seed yield; of LAD with LWR, seed yield, and RGR; and of SLA with seed yield. RGR correlated positively and significantly with CGR, but negatively and nonsignificantly with seed yield (Table 2).

This study indicates LAI and RGR are the only characters that significantly influence economic productivity of rice cultivars. ✎

Table 2. Multiple correlation of physiological parameters,^a Jabalpur, India, 1978-79.

Parameter	LAR 2	LAD 3	LWR 4	SLA 5	RGR 6	CGR 7	Yield 8
1 LAI	.881**	.892**	.855**	.329*	.080	-.116	.453**
2 LAR		.798**	.755**	.623**	.0838	.166	.558**
3 LAD			.794**	.258	.313*	-.140	.388*
4 LWR				.013	.144	.105	.453**
5 SLA					-.085	.155	.418**
6 RGR						.491**	.411*
7 CGR							.082

^a LAI = leaf area index, LAR = leaf area ratio, LAD = leaf area duration, LWR = leaf weight ratio, SLA = specific leaf area, RGR = relative growth rate, CGR = crop growth rate.

Emergence of calcium peroxide-coated rice seed at different water depths

R. Prasad and S. Singh, Division of Agronomy, Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi-110012, India

The effect of submergence depth on germination of calcium peroxide-coated seed was studied in pot culture. Plastic containers 24 cm deep and 20 cm in diameter were filled with 6 kg soil, ground to pass through 2-mm pores. Pusa 37 seeds, uncoated and coated with 40% and 64% by weight of calcium peroxide, were seeded uniformly at 100 seeds/pot. Soil was maintained either 1) in saturated condition, 2) with 1 cm standing water, 3) with 2 cm standing water, or 4) with 3 cm standing water. Each treatment had three replications.

In saturated soil, calcium peroxide coating adversely affected seed germination (see figure). Of seeds with 64% cal-

cium peroxide coating, only 12% germinated. Germination of uncoated seeds was 72%.

In standing water, germination and seedling emergence of calcium peroxide-coated seeds increased. In 1 cm standing water, more seeds germinated with 64% coating than with 40% coating. In 2 cm

standing water, the 2 coating levels were equally effective. In 3 cm standing water, fewer seeds germinated with 64% coating. As depth of standing water increased, germination and seedling emergence of uncoated rice seeds decreased. All germinated seeds emerged. ✎

Germination (%)

Effect of calcium peroxide coating on germination and seedling emergence in rice. IARI, New Delhi, India.